

D4.1 – Analysis of the data resulting from the mapping exercise and the online surveys

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The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

**GEMSTONE (101078981)-Genetically Engineering Experimental Models:
Enhancement of Scientific and Technological Excellence an Innovation Potential to
Study Neurodevelopmental Diseases**

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Introduction

GEMSTONE project aims to upgrade the research support services at Acibadem University (ACU) by improving their competencies and performance in research. Work Package 4 (WP4) aims **to tackle the imbalance in research support services between ACU and ULUND.** The objectives of WP4 are to identify the **best practices in research management and administration, improve research support capacity and efficiency, and provide customized training to staff members** involved in research support services. In the project proposal, we have explained the ACU limitations in competitive research that is significantly different from ULUND. In the SWOT analysis, the weaknesses of ACU are identified with the lack of experience in project application processes, project management, technology transfer and IP within the Research Office staff. In order to improve their capacity, we identified our methodology for strengthening the profile of ACU Research Office staff members; creating efficient support services for researchers, and strengthening researchers' soft skills. In order to implement this methodology, we planned to use a competences and skills matrix, surveys, training, mentoring, short visits, and identification of joint funding opportunities (WP4/5)¹

The methodology of WP4 consists of three phases. The first phase involves a mapping exercise to identify the policies, practices, and staff composition of research support services in both ACU and ULUND, with the aim to identify gaps and weakness at ACU. The second phase involves the transfer of best practices from ULUND to the ACU, taking into consideration the available staff and skills. The final phase involves the implementation of customized training programs for the ACU research support staff based on the results of the mapping exercise and best practices transfer.

This deliverable focuses on the first phase of WP4, which is the mapping exercise. The scope of this document is to describe the methodology, activities, and results of the mapping exercise. All other phases of WP4 will be addressed in subsequent deliverables and are not included in this report.

This deliverable will be the basis for the development of a capacity-building plan at month 8: Afterwards, the capacity-building plan will be implemented through a range of activities, such as training programs, workshops, mentoring, and coaching. These activities will address the identified capacity gaps and enhance the skills and knowledge of ACU research support staff. The project team will follow up and monitor the implementation of the capacity-building plan to ensure that it is achieving the desired outcomes addressed in the proposal. The follow-up and monitoring stage will be conducted reusing the same methodology both quantitative and qualitative, such as surveys, interviews, and focus groups.

Lessons learned from the capacity-building activities will be documented and disseminated to other universities and policy-maker authorities in Widening countries through a Best Practice Book, to be developed in the frame of WP6 at the end of the project.

By ensuring high-quality training and mentorship implications, we would like to improve the human research capacity of the research services at ACU TTO. The methodology of WP4 has crucial features which are designed with an inclusive point of view. All actors in research and research support staff at ACU has participated to the mapping exercise both in survey and focus group research.

GEMSTONE support research in the strategic areas of gene engineering technologies and neuroscience, focusing on neurodevelopmental aspects of brain disorders. Moreover, by ensuring high-quality training and mentorship implications, we would like to improve the human research capacity of the research services at ACU TTO. The methodology of WP4 has crucial features which are designed with an inclusive point of

¹ See in Table 1.2.1; Grant Agreement Part B, p.7.

view. All actors in research and research support staff at ACU has participate the mapping exercise both in survey and focus group research. Please see **the following steps in which we conceptualized our research design at WP4** assigned with the objectives explained in the Introduction part.

- 1. Assessment of current organizational capacity:** The WP4 researchers has conducted an initial assessment of the current organizational capacity of ACU in supporting research. This assessment includes an analysis of existing policies, procedures, and practices related to research management and administration. **This assessment has been identified with qualitative and quantitative research with ACU TTO staff, ACU Researcher and collaborative communication with ULUND Research Support Services.**
- 2. Identification of capacity gaps:** Based on the assessment results, the project team identified the differences between ACU and ULUND that need to be addressed **to enhance the organizational capacity of ACU research support staff in the target areas, such as grant writing and project implementation procedures engaged with international criteria.** These gaps are mostly identified with the skills and competencies of the ACU TTO unit, organisational resources and infrastructure of the university, and structured administrative procedures.
- 3. Development of capacity-building plan:** The project team will develop a capacity-building plan to address the identified gaps until the 8th month of the project. The plan will include specific objectives, activities, timelines, and responsible parties. The plan will be developed in consultation and collaboration of ULUND Research Support Staff and ICONS. The plan will be based on the conclusions of the mapping analysis.
- 4. Implementation of capacity-building activities:** The capacity-building plan will be implemented through a range of activities, such as training programs, workshops, mentoring, and coaching. These activities will address the identified capacity gaps and enhance the skills and knowledge of ACU researchers and research support staff.
- 5. Monitoring and evaluation:** The project team will follow up and monitor the implementation of the capacity-building plan to ensure that it is achieving the desired outcomes addressed in the proposal. The follow-up and monitoring stage will be conducted reusing the same methodology both quantitative and qualitative, such as surveys, interviews, and focus groups.
- 6. Dissemination of best practices:** Lessons learned from the capacity-building activities will be documented and disseminated to other universities and policy-maker authorities in Widening countries. We produce the Best Practice Book to share the knowledge and experiences gained from the experiences in GEMSTONE Project. We would like to remind that the last stage belongs to the WP6 but collects most of the data from WP4 activities.

Objectives

In the proposal, **we have designed to achieve the aim through a three-phase process, which aligns with the following objectives. In this deliverable, we only focus on the first objectives and their implementation.** For the second and third objectives with the help of the outputs of the mapping practice that we executed in the first objective's scope, restructure the procedure of our research design. Please consider the structure as a whole to clarify each step of implementation in mapping practice.

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Objective 1: Mapping competencies and skills available in research support staff, as well as policies and practices on research management and administration in the two universities, Acibadem University (ACU) and Lund University (ULUND).

- In the mapping phase, we have generated a matrix on the **competencies and skills of ACU research support services staff** (ACU Technology Transfer Office²). In order to define the gap between ACU and ULUND, firstly, **we asked the ULUND Research Services Manager about their team's skills and competencies**. Following the same notion in the competencies and skills of ULUND staff, **TTO Manager has identified the roles, responsibilities and expected skills and competencies for the position in their unit**. Through her matrix, we have discussed and **standardised the skills and competencies questionnaires** that were asked of the TTO staff at ACU. Furthermore, a focus group meeting with ACU TTO staff was executed on their roles and expectations from the collaboration with ULUND. All the qualitative and quantitative analysis has been completed and presented in this deliverable. Please see Annex 3, Competencies and Skills of ULUND Research Services Support Staff.
- In the second stage of the mapping phrase, the **ACU researchers were invited via e-mail to complete a questionnaire about their experience and evaluations of the services** provided by the ACU TTO and its staff.
- In the third stage, the **research management and administration policies and practices used at ULUND have been reviewed** through their policy documents based on their strategies in research. Moreover, **via zoom meeting organisation that two university research support staff came together**, and the **best practices were discussed** to identify how they can be successfully transferred to ACU to improve research support capacity and efficiency.

Objective 2: Identifying weaknesses, knowledge and skills gap, and best practices to improve research support capacity and efficiency. This stage will be start after the results and the analysis are shared with the consortium and all the stakeholders of WP4 at ACU and ULUND. The plan of tasks to reach this objective will be completed in the eightieth month of the project.

- The implementation phase is **based on the results of the mapping phase**, and a plan for the training and capacity building of the research support services staff will be elaborated. **The plan will include traditional training, mentorship, and short-term visits for selected staff members**. These measures aim to **address the weaknesses, knowledge and skills gap, and best practices identified in the mapping phase**.

Objective 3: Offering training, mentoring, and short visits opportunities to the staff involved in research support services at ACU to address the weaknesses, gaps, and best practices identified

- We called this stage as **follow-up phase** which will involve self-evaluation questionnaires administered to ACU research support staff at 18th month. This will check if the training and support

² Ibid.

measures applied contributed time to reaching the expected impact, such as new competencies and skills acquired, increased confidence, and new perceived strengths and weaknesses.

Overall, the methodology aims to improve the research support capacity and efficiency at ACU through a comprehensive process that identifies knowledge and skills gaps, implements appropriate training measures, and monitors the impact of these measures over

The methodology of WP4 involves a participatory approach, where stakeholders will be actively involved in the assessment, planning, implementation, and evaluation of capacity-building activities. The aim is to ensure that the project outcomes are relevant, effective, and sustainable and that ACU researchers are better equipped to compete at the European level in getting funded from international programmes.

Activities

In this point, we address the **Objective 1** and **1st and 2nd conceptualized steps in research design, the methodology for WP4 of GEMSTONE** until the end of 6th month, March 2023, **involved a series of sequential steps to gather information and insights from project stakeholders.** All the steps have organized and the data from all participants collected by the Project Manager, Sinem Bağçe. Please see the Figure 1 to follow the timeline of the activities.

- First of all, the **ACU TTO Manager, Eda Tanoğlu, prepared a skill and competencies matrix for TTO employees.**
- **The Project Manager contacted with Rickard Eksten** who is responsible for the tasks belongs to ULUND under WP4 and explained the tasks and duties of the team in WP4. Rickard Eksten has sent competencies and skills required in their office, the roles and responsibilities of each members at ULUND Research Services. Also, he shared the policy documents of ULUND about research management related with their unit
- This matrix was standardised by Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner (WP4 Leader) by comparing the ACU TTO Manager documents on roles, responsibilities, skills and competencies documents prepared by ULUND Research Support Services Manager. The matrix was standardized as survey questions and asked ACU TTO staff via e-mail. Please see Table 1 for the specific questions asked to TTO employees.
- This matrix sent to TTO staff and the data collected.
- Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner (WP4 Leader) analysed the data of skill and competencies of TTO staff.
- Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner prepared a short survey questions to ACU Researchers to ask their experiences with ACU TTO and evaluations
- The Project Manager sent the survey to ACU Researcher and collected the data.
- In parallel, Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner conducted a separate focus group study with TTO employees, and a face-to-face interview with the TTO Manager, Eda Tanoğlu, to gather their perspectives on the skills and competencies needed for effective TTO services.
- Under confidentiality, the data in face-to-face interview with the TTO are staff transcript by Medicine School Assistants. Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner coded and analysed them (see Table 2).
- Lastly, the ACU TTO staff had an online meeting with Lund University Research Support Services. This meeting was organized as the last part of the Task 4.1 and 4.2 by the Project Manager. The presentations were on their specific services, such as Rickard Eksten, Research Funding Advisor, Research Services, Fariba Vaziri-Sani, Project Manager, LU Cooperation Office, Per Mercke, Patent Advisor, LU Innovation.

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- All the results are analysed with WP4 team leading by Assoc. Prof Melike Şahiner and started to prepare reporting.

The Workflow of the Research Design (Quantitative and Qualitative)

As it is seen in Figure 1, the ACU's research support services were evaluated through a holistic approach, as Task 4.1 Mapping exercise (M1-6) and 4.2 Surveys (M1-6) were executed simultaneously during the implementation phase. In summary of the activities in previous section, there are three sides (actors) of our research in WP4. At the beginning, The ULUND mapped the research management and administration policies and practices in use and mapping question for TTO staff prepared. Simultaneously, the staff composition, competencies, and skills available were also collected to create a competence/skill matrix. Self-evaluation questionnaires were administered to the ACU research support staff to formalize their learning needs, career situations, perceived limitations, and strengths. Focus group interviews were provided to identify the need and requirements to improve research support capacity and efficiency in the ACU TTO services. The ACU researchers completed a dedicated questionnaire to identify their feelings and expectations regarding the services provided.

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Task 4.1 Mapping exercise (M1-6). Leader: ACU. Participating: ULUND				Task 4.2 Surveys (M1-6) Leader: ACU		
T4.1	Data of Research Support Staff at ACU & ULUND		Analysing Policies and Identification of Best Practices	Identification of Best Practices	Data of ACU Researchers	
	Creation of a template to collect data on staff composition, knowledge and skills		ULUND was map the research management and administration policies and practices in use (e.g. responsibilities and role of the different offices, interactions methodology with researchers, project quality assessment procedures, project management software/tools etc.)	These results, together with their comments, will form the infrastructure for T4.2 and T4.3, it is important that the positive aspects and features that need to be developed are clearly included in the report, individual development mentoring etc. will be arranged over the features to be developed, while trainings will be organized.	Identifying the feelings and expectations of the researcher from ACU who had contact with research support services	This was a parallel study with T4.1. The ACU researchers (among those supported in the past by the ACU research support services) were invited to complete a dedicated questionnaire about their experience and expectations on the services provided by the offices and their respective staff.
	Completion of template collecting data on staff composition, knowledge and skills	Collaboration with Lund University Research Services+ Data related to staff composition(e.g. number of staff, seniority mix, academic background, functions,) and competences and skills available will be collected from the staff members within the offices supporting the research at ACU				
	A competence/skill matrix was being created. + focus group interviews with TTO staff	In parallel, self-evaluation questionnaires will be administered to ACU research support services staff to formalise their learning needs, their career situation, the perceived limitations and strengths.				
	Creation and administration of the self-evaluation questionnaires to ACU research support staff	Compared with those collected from the relevant offices at ULUND and ICONS (e.g. Research Project Office, Grant Offices, Grant management Unit, innovation departments, administration units, TTO).	Identifying the best practices that may be successfully transferred to ACU (in consideration with the available staff and skills) to improve research support capacity and efficiency.	Definition of the framework for the identification policies and practices in research management and administration	Preparation and distribution of the online survey	
	Collection of data coming from self-evaluation questionnaires				Analysis, interpretation and reporting of the data collected in T4.2	
Analysis of the data from self-evaluation questionnaires +focus group results						

Figure 1: The workflow of Task 4.1 and 4.2

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Initial assessment of the current organisational capacity at ACU

This section presents only the data detected under WP4's tasks that demonstrate the research support services capability provided under the ACU TTO. All comparative analysis of ACU and ULUND is available in the "Comparison between ACU TTO and ULUND Support Services" section.

There are notable differences in the organizational structures of ACU TTO and ULUND Research Services. ULUND Support Services primarily focuses on project development services, including the management of intellectual property rights in Horizon Europe Programmes specifically assigned to the faculties, whereas the Research Office under ACU TTO primarily provides project management services for national funds, with less emphasis on international programs. It is worth noting that during the project proposal preparation process, ACU TTO was not yet fully structured and was known as the ACU Research Projects Offices.

When ACU TTO was re-established in December 2022, it was deemed appropriate to serve in the modules defined by The Scientific And Technological Research Council of Turkiye (TÜBİTAK) for TTOs³. Considering its own unique conditions, it has defined the bio-design service required for health projects and start-ups as an additional module.

TÜBİTAK has defined TTO activities through five modules as follows:

Module 1: Awareness, Publicity, Information, and Training Services: The objective of this module is to provide information about technology and innovation, particularly in the context of businesses conducting R&D projects and developing projects in cooperation with universities. The activities carried out within this module include organizing training events, conducting various information events for university-industry cooperation, and introducing competencies, resources, and cooperation opportunities, among other things.

Module 2: Services for Benefitting from Support Programs: This module involves informing universities and businesses about various grant support programs and providing project design and administrative support. The production of new information and knowledge under the roof of the university within the scope of research projects technologies, licensing, and commercialization is also an important input for this module.

Module 3: Project Development/Management Services (University-Industry Cooperation Activities): This module focuses on utilizing academic knowledge in private sector R&D projects. TTO provides coordination services, such as finding researchers, establishing contracts for cooperation, and determining and projecting the needs of the project.

Module 4: Intellectual Property Rights Management and Licensing Services: This module involves the identification of projects and studies that can be considered within the scope of intellectual property, confidentiality, know-how, registration, and property management. Decision-making, registration transactions (utility model, patent, etc.), marketing, licensing, and transmission of usage information to the user/customer are done in this module.

Module 5: Incorporation and Entrepreneurship Services: This module supports the commercialization of new products and technologies developed by academicians. It involves supporting entrepreneurial activities and providing services such as consultancy, training on project design, marketing, legal and administrative transactions, etc.

³ <https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/sites/default/files/1601-cagri-metni-2017.pdf> (not available in English)

Skill and Competencies Matrix (SCM) of ACU TTO Staff

The SCM was carried out within the scope of the GEMSTONE project to evaluate the employees and working environments that directly or indirectly supported the researchers in our university in their scientific grant applications, project management and administrative procedures. The participants were asked to evaluate themselves and the team they worked with using a scale ranging from 0-5 as indicated in the form. The participants were asked about the resources and limitations they could use while performing the specified qualifications. In the explanation column, they were given the opportunity to write down any topics that were not mentioned, but they wanted to specify. The answers in this document were not shared with any third parties, and the data to be used was expressed as completely anonymous. The participants were recommended to fill out the form alone and in a quiet environment. By considering, personal data protection procedures, all the data collected in this survey were anonymized and stored in the GEMSTONE computer at ACU.

Please see the scale under the Table 1 that we request TTO staff evaluate themselves and their team (see Table 1 last rows). As you can see in Table 1, 34 competencies were asked in 6 dimensions and with skill and attitudes in 27 items.

Table 1: SCM of ACU TTO Staff (Competency Level-Individual and Competency Level- Team)

Dimensions		Skills and Competencies
D1. Dimensions of Research (Infrastructure, HR, Tools, Ecosystem) Refers to Module 1, 2 and 3	1	Provides consultancy on project cycle management
	2	Recognizes modules in technology transfer and establishes the relationship between jobs
	3	Explain and use terms in research projects and technology transfer
	4	Recognizes the needs of the target group and directs them to the relevant specialist in the office, to the relevant unit outside the office, and to the appropriate service/person in the ecosystem if it is to be solved outside the institution.
	5	Develops new tools/methods/training programs suitable for the research needs of the target group
D2. Fund Information - Fund Management Refers to Module 1, 2 and 3	1	Recognizes all research funds (internal, national, international, private sector sources), explains the necessary information in detail, organizes activities for its dissemination
	2	Researches new sources of funding, learns flow, announces and directs
	3	Recognize researchers and work areas to establish project teams for research funds
	4	Builds in-house research teams for multidisciplinary research funding
	5	Recognizes the right stakeholders in the ecosystem to engage in external collaborations on research funding
	6	Establishes external research teams/consortiums for research funds involving multiple disciplines/institutions/stakeholders
	7	Recognizes intellectual property outputs supported by research funds, guides inventors for further progress
	8	Recognizes entrepreneurial fund support, directs business ideas to the relevant channel
	9	It determines the technology readiness level of the defined project/business idea, and offers suggestions for moving to the next stage.

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D3. Financial and Human Resources Management of Funds Refers to Administrative Services in Grant Management	1	Recognizes the processes of all research funding support after the contract process, guides the executive about the flow of the next works (financial, administrative, etc.)
	2	Recognizes and processes electronic tracking systems of funds
	3	Financial, human resources, procurement, etc. of their projects. carries out its work in coordination with the relevant unit
D4. University-Industry Cooperation Refers to Module 3	1	Provides consultancy on all R&D-oriented funds and other tools needed for the works to be done within the scope of university-industry cooperation (UIL) with companies.
	2	The company conducts interviews, defines the companies' R&D needs, matches the company's opportunities
	3	Keeps the list of laboratory facilities up-to-date to present to companies in university-industry collaborations
	4	Cooperates with other units of the university in establishing other collaborations (internship, laboratory use, testing services, etc.) with the university.
D5. Intellectual Property Rights Management Refers to Module 4	1	Provides consultancy on intellectual property rights
	2	Follows the intellectual property rights pool
	3	Takes initiatives to increase the Technology Readiness (TRL) of inventions in the intellectual property pool
	4	Advises on the commercialization of inventions
D6. Entrepreneurship - Incubation Activities Refers to Module 5	1	Provides consultancy on the educational, administrative and financial processes of entrepreneurship
	2	It carries out all financial and legal processes of TEKMER ⁴ company in cooperation with the relevant units.
	3	Organizes awareness events within the institution for the purpose of announcing and disseminating academic entrepreneurship.
	4	Organizes awareness events on mentoring academic staff
	5	Carries out the administrative work of the Incubation Centre (TEKMER) (use of the halls, lease negotiations and contract transactions of TEKMER, tracking of rent payments and invoices, administrative support in licensing procedures, other administrative infrastructure needs of entrepreneurs, etc.).
	6	Recommends the relevant initiatives to the Innovation Commission of Acıbadem Healthcare Group and makes the necessary preparations
	1	Provides consultancy on the workflows of the Bio design Centre, recognizes the relevant forms

⁴ TEKMER is a company running as the incubation center of ACU TTO. TEKMER is a structure that provides services to technology/innovation-focused entrepreneurs or businesses with one or more related themes and research and development and/or product/process/service innovation.

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D7. Bio-design Activities Refers to Module 6	2	It collects the requests coming to the Bio design Centre, passes the pre-selection, R&D and Intellectual Property Exchange. Prepares to present to the Commission
	3	Prepares the catalogue of the Bio design Centre and keeps it up to date
D8. Skills and Attitude Refers to expected skills in all TTO services	1	Follows workflows
	2	Has scientific literacy skills
	3	Has the ability to work in a team
	4	Reads projects in accordance with the rules
	5	Follows the legislation required by the job
	6	Makes an effective presentation
	7	Prepares reports in accordance with the rules
	8	He has the appropriate consultancy and mentoring skills.
	9	Has business development skills
	10	It can carry out negotiations in accordance with the agreements.
	11	Demonstrates appropriate communication skills
	12	Uses the English language well
	13	Uses electronic tracking systems appropriate to the subject.
	14	Creates, archives and reports appropriate data on its subject
	15	Defines the need for R&D
	16	Manages contract processes
	17	Dominates the commercialization processes of scientific data
	18	manages funds
	19	Compatible in teamwork ⁵
	20	Is prone to multidisciplinary work
	21	Receives feedback and exhibits appropriate behaviour
	22	Develops a sense of belonging
	23	Cares and transfers new knowledge
	24	Prepares all tasks on time and delivers on schedule
	25	Demonstrates the attitude that will initiate the interaction the job needs
	26	respects fairness
	27	Demonstrates the ability to work collaboratively between departments and institutions

The Results of the Matrix (SCM)

An 8-person competencies and skills matrix was created with the active participation of TTO employees. The reference threshold for the manager responses and TTO services were analysed separately. The employees were asked to evaluate themselves and their team in terms of the specified skills and attitudes. The left graph below displays the average self-evaluation of the employees, allowing for a comparison of the self-evaluation average with the reference and the manager. Meanwhile, the right graph indicates how each employee evaluated their team on the relevant items.

To read the figures below, please consider that *D* indicates the dimensions in the first column of Table 1, *ind* means self-evaluation average of ACU TTO staff and *team* shows the average grade for the evaluation of TTO team as a whole. **It is should be emphasized in this point that some of the competencies in modules do not reflect the administrative staff responsibilities, such as human resource and financial**

⁵ This expression is understood as a skill, differ from *has the ability to work in a team (D9 I3)*.

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management of the funded project. Therefore, the average level of some the items in Table 1 might be lower than it is expected. However, we asked all the questions to all staff of TTO to understand their competencies that are open to development.

While reading the graphs below, consider the expressions on the 0-5 scale. Level 3 means that the task is done at the expected level. Thus, 4 and 5 indicate above-expected proficiency and are areas of improvement for expected locals.

However, when examining all dimensions of the qualifications matrix, it was found that the reference values of the office were very high, making it difficult to provide a development area. In other words, it is not appropriate to expect this level at the 5th level in a structure whose definition cannot be carried beyond the expected level of a clear proficiency. For example, the expectation of almost perfect communication skills in the dimension 8 is incompatible with real-life situations. Therefore, it is important to review and revise reference proficiency levels in the future, and to evaluate the results of this study together with office managers to make future plans.

Table 2: The Scale for the Evaluation of the Competencies and Skill Matrix of the ACU TTO Staff

0- This topic is not related to my field of study
1- I don't know about this subject;
2- I have knowledge about the subject, but I cannot manage it without help
3- I can carry out the relevant process at the expected level;
4- I can carry out and develop the relevant process completely
5- I am competent enough to re-plan the relevant process

Figure 2: Dimension1: Research (Infrastructure, HR, Tools, Ecosystem)

The results suggest that ACU TTO staff and TTO Manager have varying levels of self-perceived competence in different dimensions of research and technology transfer. In Dimension 1, **both managers and TTO employees see themselves as highly competent in the sub-group competencies related to research infrastructure, human resources, tools, and ecosystem.** However, they evaluated the team as being able to plan, rather than fully carry out and develop the relevant processes.

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Figure 3: Dimension 2- Fund Information and Fund Management

In dimension 2, TTO employees do not consider themselves highly competent in funding information and project management. However, they evaluate the team as being able to carry out related processes above what is expected. This indicates that the team may be compensating for individual weaknesses by working together effectively.

Figure 4: Dimension 3- Financial and Human Resources Management of Funds

In Dimension 3, both managers and TTO employees perceive themselves and the team as highly competent in the management of funds, financial and human resources. This suggests that the team has a strong foundation in this area.

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Figure 5: Dimention4- University-Industry Cooperation

In Dimension 4, TTO employees do not perceive themselves as competent in university-industry cooperation, but they evaluate the team as competent. The manager, on the other hand, considers himself fully competent in one subfield and as expected in others. This highlights the need for more training and development in this area for individual employees.

Figure 6: Dimention5- Intellectual Property Rights Management

In Dimension 5, TTO employees evaluate individual competencies in intellectual property rights management as low compared to the reference. However, they evaluate the team as competent at the expected level. This may indicate that the team's overall competence in this area is satisfactory, despite individual weaknesses.

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Figure 7: Dimention6- Entrepreneurship - Incubation Activities

In Dimensions 6 and 7, TTO employees consider entrepreneurship and bio design activities as not related to their work area, but they evaluate the team as sufficient at a certain level. This suggests that the team has a general awareness of these areas, but if necessary they may need more training and development to fully engage in these activities.

Figure 8: Dimention7- Bio-design Activities

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Figure

9: Dimention8- Self-evaluation of team members on Skills and Attitudes

In Dimension 8, which includes 27 sub-domain qualifications related to professional skills and attitudes, TTO employees consider themselves more competent in some areas than others. However, their evaluation of team performance lags behind in some sub-areas. This indicates the need for further training and development in these areas to improve team performance as a whole.

Overall, the results of this study suggest that the TTO team has a strong foundation in certain areas, such as the management of funds and financial and human resources. However, there is room for improvement in other areas, such as university-industry cooperation, intellectual property rights management, and professional skills and attitudes. The findings highlight the need for targeted training and development programs to address individual weaknesses and improve team performance as a whole.

Until here, all dimensions were interpreted in general. Each item will be discussed in the conclusion section together with the complementary data of the focus group research outputs.

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Figure 10: Dimension9- Evaluation of team members on Skills and Attitudes

Qualitative Phase- The Focus Group Research with ACU TTO Staff

In this qualitative phase of the study, a **case study approach** was selected to investigate the current situation of TTO office workers and to identify areas for future development. Case studies can be conducted using a qualitative or quantitative approach, both of which aim to reveal results related to a specific situation. Using

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both approaches, we conducted an in-depth investigation of one or more cases, exploring factors related to a situation (such as environment, individuals, events, and processes) with a holistic approach focused on how they affect the relevant situation and how they are impacted by it⁶.

On January 25, 2023, Assoc. Prof Melike Sahiner conducted the focus group research with 8 ACU TTO staff. All of the analysed data of the focus group were read and 48 codes were obtained in 12 categories in 5 main themes. A blind researcher has double checked the anonymized data. Coding was done and progressed. Please see the coding of the expressions of the ACU TTO Staff during the focus group research (see Table 2).

To accomplish this, we organized a face-to-face focus group with 8 TTO employees to better understand their competencies, and the aspects they intend to develop throughout the GEMSTONE project. The interviews were recorded and transcribed into a Word document, with anonymity assured by converting name information into codes. The transcriptions were then analysed using coding to identify categories and create code definitions. Categories were determined with the codes created, and information about codes and categories was reduced to themes. The resulting data in Table 1 will be discussed in the conclusion section. It should be noted that the recordings were analysed by an independent researcher, and the data obtained will only be used for research and development purposes without being shared with third parties.

The following questions were posed during the focus group interview:

1. Can you briefly introduce yourself and describe your role and role in the office where you work?
2. Basically, what are your competencies in the work you do, do you have any aspects that you intend to improve about them?
3. What are the difficulties/difficulties you have experienced during your task and do you have any plans or suggestions to overcome them?
4. What do you expect from the cooperation between LUND and ICONS?

Table 3: Coding sheet of the focus group data

Theme	Category	Code #	Code	Participant	#
Area of Responsibility	Basic Missions	1	process implementation and monitoring	K01, K02, KO4,	3
		2	process consultancy and implementation and follow-up	KO3, KO5, KO6,	3
		3	process management, consulting and implementation	K07, KO8	2
		4	reporting	K01, K02, KO4,	3

⁶ John W. Creswell (2018), Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches. Sage Publications, California, ISBN: 9781412916066, 9781412916073

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	Final active work done	5	development	KO3,	1	
		6	development/reporting	KO5, KO6, KO7, KO8	4	
	Experience Level	7	experienced	KO1, KO5, KO6, KO7, KO8	5	
		8	intermediate experienced	KO2, KO3,	2	
		9	inexperienced	KO4,	1	
	Core competencies (personally identified)	Competency Level	10	come from a multidisciplinary background	KO3, KO8	2
			11	mastery of health field studies	KO3, KO5, KO4,	3
			12	scientific literacy	KO3, KO6,	2
			13	competent and experienced	KO3, KO4, KO1, KO7, KO2,KO8	6
14			successful in communication	KO1,	1	
15			knowing what a project is	KO2, KO5, KO4,	3	
16			have work experience	KO3, KO6, KO7, KO5, KO8	5	
17		getting to know academics	KO4, KO8	1		
Development Area		18	English language	KO1, KO2, KO3, KO4, KO5,	5	
		19	project management	KO4, KO5, KO6, KO7,	4	
	20	domination of EU projects	KO1, KO2	2		
Difficulties Encountered	Experienced difficulty	21	lack of institutional memory	KO1, KO2, KO7, KO6, KO8	5	
		22	lack of work flow charts, slowness	KO6, KO3, KO8	3	
		23	uncertainty of job distribution	KO6, KO7	2	
		24	not being recognized by internal stakeholders	KO6, KO5, KO8	3	
		25	excessive workload	KO2, KO3, KO1, KO7,	4	
		26	lack of staff	KO1, KO7, KO8	3	
		27	deficiencies in directives, regulations	KO6, KO3, KO5, KO8	4	
	Action Taken to Overcome	28	renewed approach	KO6, KO8	2	
		29	preparations for renewal	KO6, KO8	2	
		30	individual efforts	KO2, KO7,	2	

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	Plan or Suggestions	31	get counselling	K01,	1
		32	Expanding the team	K02, K01, K07, K08	4
		33	Job descriptions should be made	K06, K01, K05,	3
		34	Basic framework should be determined	K06, K01, K07, K05, K08	5
		35	Promotions should be made	K06, K05, K08	3
		36	Realistic performance metrics and rewards	K01, K05, K03, K08	4
Lund cooperation	Questions for cooperation	37	Different operating systems	K05, K01, K06, K08	4
		38	Integration within the research structure	K05,	1
		39	ways to motivate researchers	K05, K01,	2
		40	ways to overcome difficulties	K05, K06, K08	3
	Expectation from cooperation	41	to monitor the processes in place, to learn	K05, K07, K01, K06	4
		42	establish a collaboration	K06, K07, K08	3
		43	improve the English language	K01,	1
		44	to be a guide	K01, K02, K03, K04, K05, K06, K07, K08	8
Communication with researchers	Contacted academic group	45	academics with an entrepreneurial spirit	K07, K08	2
		46	all academics	K01, K04, K06, K03, K08	5
	Communication level	47	positive communication	K07, K01, K04, K08	1
		48	negative communication	K01, K04, K06, K03, K08	5

Online Survey with ACU Researchers

As part of the GEMSTONE project, a study was conducted to evaluate the employees and working environments that directly or indirectly support researchers in our university with the aim of improving the support services. To further refine the framework for identifying policies and practices in research management and administration, **an identification matrix extended with the ACU Researchers who had contact with ACU TTO**. Then, a survey was distributed to gather their experiences and evaluations. At this point, our most important shortcoming is that we have received feedback from very few researchers, On the other hand, although their number is low, it is also understood that they are in close contact with the TTO due to a large number of the national researches they implemented.

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The participants were assured that their responses would be kept anonymous and would not be shared with any third parties. The data collected from the survey was used to inform a subsequent focus group meeting, where the findings were discussed in detail.

Researchers were asked to share their experiences and provide feedback on the quality of the services provided by ACU TTO. The survey responses were used to identify strengths and areas for improvement, which were later discussed in the focus group meeting

You can find the list of technical knowledge, skills and attitude competencies in the questions that will evaluate the service received in the following project processes on the second page.

Table 4: List of questions asked to the ACU Researchers

Briefly explain the details of your contact with the Project Office (it is expected to provide the name of the project, type, completion status, project process information and the support of the project office in these areas):
When you think of the service you received by the project office in your project processes;
What are the strongest points in terms of technical knowledge in the service provided?
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of technical information in the service provided?
What are the strongest strengths in terms of skills in the service delivered?
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of skills in the service provided?
What are the strongest aspects in terms of attitude characteristics in the service provided?
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of attitude characteristics in the service provided?
If there are other topics you would like to add, please write them in this field.

This survey was distributed via e-mail by Project Manager Sinem Bağçe and then Assoc. Dr. Melike Şahin to 50 researchers who received services from ACU TTO. However, only 8 researchers completed the survey and provided feedback. While this sample size is not sufficient, it suggests that those who responded are individuals who are willing to share their opinions about TTO services.

Our online survey gathered responses from ACU Researchers. We can say that there is an emerged consensus among these researchers regarding the essential qualities of TTO services. Specifically, respondents emphasized the importance of technical knowledge, professional skills, and attitudes in TTO team members. Effective communication and adherence to project timelines were also highlighted, along with the need to address the challenges associated with excessive workloads through the employment of specialists. We had the same responses in focus group research with TTO staff, too.

While the researchers identified project follow-up as a strength of the TTO staff, they also noted the importance of needed improvement in project development. Notably, our study did not include respondents with experience in international project implementation. As a parallel finding in the research with TTO staff, it is revealed that while the team are well-experienced and qualified in internal scientific fund and the national funds, such as TUBİTAK and TUSEB; they do not have experience in international fund management. The answers provided to the questionnaire are available in Table 5 below.

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Table 5: Results of the Questioners asked the ACU Researchers

Questions asked	Main points indicated from the answers
What are the strongest points in terms of technical knowledge in the service provided?	eager team
	mastery of process management
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of technical information in the service provided?	lack of reporting
	lack of staff
	continuous improvement
	mastery of project development and writing stages
What are the strongest strengths in terms of skills in the service delivered?	workflow tracking
	communication skill
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of skills in the service provided?	scientific literacy
	using regulatory knowledge
What are the strongest aspects in terms of attitude characteristics in the service provided?	time appropriate work
	harmonious teamwork
What are the aspects that need to be developed in terms of attitude characteristics in the service provided?	multidisciplinary study
	do not cooperate
	receiving feedback and acting accordingly
If there are other topics you would like to add, please write them in this field.	developments required in project development
	specialized workforce should be increased

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Comparison between ACU TTO and ULUND Support Services

From the analysis of the data collected through this questionnaire, it emerged a consensus among researchers regarding the essential qualities of TTO services. Specifically, respondents emphasized the importance of technical knowledge, professional skills, and attitudes in TTO team members. Effective communication and adherence to project timelines were also highlighted, along with the need to address the challenges associated with excessive workloads through the employment of specialists. We had the same responses in focus group research with TTO staff, too.

While the researchers identified project follow-up as a strength of the TTO staff, they also noted the importance of needed improvement in project development.

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Assoc Prof. Melike Şahiner and the Project Manager Sinem Bağçe have two online meeting with ULUND Research Services to discuss the WP4 tasks and understand the structures and services of research support units. After all the qualitative and quantitative research completed, the ACU TT

Figure 11: Acibadem University Technology Transfer Office

O staff had a productive online meeting with Lund University Research Support Services on March 9th, 2023. This meeting was organized as the last part of the Task 4.1 and 4.2. The goal of the meeting was to discuss the initial situation to support high-quality research. The presentations delivered by Rickard Eksten,

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Per Mercke, and Fariba Vaziri-Sani were on their specific services. The similarities and differences provided by Lund University to support researchers were discussed, and opportunities for future collaboration were explored. We would like to present the analysis of all the collaborative activities in this section.

It would be useful to briefly explain the structure and services of ACU TTO to give a notion of the relation within the objectives of the WP4 that provide to develop the services of the ACU TTO and improve its personnel.

Figure 10 shows that ACU TTO is comprised 4 main components under 6 modules (as stated in the Introduction section). The Research-Based Jobs component has a total of 3 staff members, including 1 experienced staff member in project development, 1 junior staff member for IP management, and 1 junior national fund responsible person. The Administrative-Based Jobs component includes staff members who are all experienced in final and human resource management of both internal and national funding procedures. The TEKMER Company, which serves as an incubation centre for the TTO, has 1 senior and 1 junior personnel. The Bio-design Centre has only 1 senior staff member who is experienced in their niche working field.

ACU TTO consists of six module-based structures under a Rectorate administrative unit (see Figure 1). Only the incubation services under TTO are established with a private corporation called TEKMER. First of all, **it should be underlined that the ACU TTO staff organizational chart is different from that of Lund University**). The ULUND Research Services has 9 senior staff that are highly competent. For instance, 5 of them have PhD degrees in the field of they give support services. While 7 of the are experts in international funds, especially Horizon Europe programmes, 2 of them specialized in Swedish funds (please see Annex 2). However, for ACU TTO, the competencies could not be provided in detail. The roles and responsibilities of the staff based on skills and knowledge are given in Annex 4.

ACU TTO is a small-scale office with different types of modules and each module has a small team that is responsible for all aspects of the project management process. Moreover, **there is no staff specifically assigned to project development**. Since January 2023, ACU TTO had been structured as Scientific Project Office at ACU. In December 2022, all the modules are united under ACU TTO. Therefore, comparing ACU TTO with the Lund Research Support Services, in terms of project development support services scope, especially in international funds, might not be fair in a straightforward manner. For instance, only one staff member is responsible for EU projects in ACU TTO, and she is not specialized in just one area of EU funds (such as ERC or MSC). Whereas, in Lund Research Support Services, each staff has their own expertise in specific international funds, such as ERC, MSCA, and clusters.

Lund University has a bottom-up approach to research management that emphasizes unit-level responsibility for policy advice and regulation. This approach gives each unit within the university a significant degree of autonomy, which can be beneficial in promoting innovation and agility in response to changing research needs. In contrast, the statement suggests that ACU may not have the same degree of bottom-up autonomy in research management as Lund University.

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Table 6: Main Difference between ACU TTO and ULUND Research Services

ACU TTO	ULUND Research Services
Has general research strategic plan, but does not specify the each component of research and development	Has a detailed strategic plan for research and development ⁷
Does not have a policy document specifically identifying the roles and responsibilities of each module and staff	Has policy documents for the roles, responsibilities and procedures of their services.
responsible for IP-based outputs of research, and commercialization activities.	Has another TTO unit for each IP and commercialization apart from research services
responsible for the grant management process, majorly administrative and financial aspects	The grant management unit is a different unit, research services only focus on project development ⁸
Does not have a project development office. There is only one competent staff for project development in national funds.	Responsible for grant development procedure until the grant agreement signed
Does not have a specific focus on international funds, such as Erasmus+, partnerships and Horizon Europe.	Mainly responsible for Horizon Europe project development. The office has specific experts in Horizon Europe clusters and programs under scientific excellence ⁹
Has university-industry collaborations based on funds and consultancy services for the industry based on contracts	Does not give any services for university-industry collaboration
Has bio-design services	Does not have such a design service under research services.
Mostly structured its services around the TUBITAK TTO model based on modules- a top-down approach.	Structured its services based on needs and requirements of research sustainability based on a bottom-up approach (grant applications and competitiveness in science)

Different from LUND University, ACU does not have a specifically prepared strategic plan for research. ACU has strategic aims and priorities for research areas in general.

The 2019-2023 Strategic Plan for ACU University Research and Development outlines several objectives, including:

1. Increasing the annual number of publications in international indexes for Acıbadem Mehmet Ali Aydınlar University.

⁷ Lund University Strategic Plan 2017-2026: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/strategic-plan-2017-2026.pdf>
Lund University Research strategy 2017-2022: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2022-01/research-strategy-2017-2021.pdf> (this is currently being updated)

⁸ General information on our support on research funding: <https://www.staff.lu.se/research-and-education/research-support/research-funding>

⁹ Joint support for the University's participation in the EU framework programme: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2021-07/Joint-support-for-the-Universitys-participation-in-Horizon%20Europe.pdf>

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2. Increasing the number of scientific research projects supported by national and international institutions and international multicentre studies.
3. Supporting postgraduate and medical specialization students in participating in research activities abroad.
4. Expanding the number of research centres and laboratories and improving the infrastructure of existing ones.
5. Increasing the financial support provided by the university for scientific research.

In addition to these objectives, the university aims **to encourage research in priority areas, apply for domestic and international funds to access external financial resources, strengthen the Technology Transfer Office**, establish a structure to provide patent support, update the Academic Incentive System Directive, increase the number of undergraduate and graduate programs in foreign languages, employ joint faculty members from abroad (Joint Affiliation), establish research and development cooperation protocols with foreign universities, and strengthen the structures of multidisciplinary practice and research centres to ensure their continuity and diversity.

While Lund University has broad fields of research, ACU is a small-scale thematic university. Therefore, the focus is majorly on health and complementary fields in social science, such as psychology and sociology and also engineering, such as mechatronic and bioengineering. The university's research policy documents and their links are as follows¹⁰.

The University R&D Priority Areas are as follows:

1. Neuroscience
2. Biotechnology
 - a. Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering
 - b. Medical Biotechnology
 - c. Pharmaceutical Biotechnology
3. Cancer Research
4. Rare Diseases
5. Biomedical Research
 - a. Medical Device
 - b. Biomedical Imaging
 - c. Computational fields (Bioinformatics)
6. Health Policies
7. Basic Science Research

¹⁰ https://www.acibadem.edu.tr/assets/kp/acu-arastirma-gelistirme-alan-oncelikleri_1g.pdf (Not available in English)

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Research, Collaboration & Innovation

Figure 12: Lund University Research Support Services Units

The most important difference is the project development services. Lund University offers a range of project development services related to EU financing. These include information seminars and individual meetings at any stage of interest for those who are curious about EU financing. For those interested in writing an application, the university provides initial facilitating information, tips, and templates through individual meetings, as well as start-up and writing packages, additional information about announcements, tips and feedback on call match, consortium and draft applications, and help with budget and co-financing calculation. The university also answers administrative questions and portal issues related to EU financing.

For projects that have been approved, Lund University offers contract preparations and contract issues services, as well as an initial meeting with a researcher and an administrator/economist. The university provides support in reporting and preparation for the audit, and planning and coordination grants. In the case of rejected applications, the university offers a review of the EU evaluation protocol and provides support for the development of a new application (See annexe 2 for more information).

Different from LUND University, ACU TTO is responsible for IP-based outputs of research, and commercialization activities. Above mentioned Directive is followed for these kinds of IP-based processes.

ACU Directive for Intellectual Property (Invention), Production and Consulting Services of Academic Staff (A revised version is on the Commission's Agenda, after the approval of the new version, the target group of this Directive will be not only the academic staff but also the students and administrative staff). **ACU TTO is responsible for following the IP of academic staff and administrative staff.** R&D and IP Commission is responsible for evaluating IP rights and payments, and also consultancy services for university-industry collaborations. All the agreement procedure, payments, registration of IPs, and commercialization activities are under the responsibility of TTO. IP pool is managed by the TTO in the name of Commission, and negotiations for commercialization of IPs are followed by TTO¹¹.

¹¹ <https://kms.kaysis.gov.tr/Home/Kurum/60061509> (Not available in English).

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Different from LUND University, ACU TTO is responsible for creating cooperative actions between firms and following administrative process of consultancy services for university-industry collaborations. Above mentioned Directive is followed for these kind of university-industry collaboration processes, as well.

ACU Directive for The Academic Activity Support Commission¹² - (Internal Fund) evaluates the budgets requested for congresses, scientific meetings and publication activities, meetings and training for development purposes, and approves the appropriateness of granting appropriations from the relevant academic year budget. Regular faculty members and students can apply for this support. Supports are for:

1. Domestic and international scientific meeting participation support for lecturers/students
2. Scientific meeting organization support for academic units
3. For the articles of faculty members accepted for publication in WOS Q1 and Q2 categories, such as English article editing support and Article publishing support (see Annex1).

Different from LUND University, ACU TTO is responsible for following all steps of the internal research fund shortly called AFDK. Above mentioned Directive is followed for this kind of internal funds supporting congresses, scientific meetings and publication activities, meetings and training.

Conclusion

In this report, we presented the data collection process of the skills and competency matrix of ACU TTO staff, and results of the surveys and the focus group discussions on the skills, knowledge level, and team dynamics of the staff and ACU Researchers. Moreover, in this deliverable, we tried to compare ACU and ULUND research support. However, it is important to note that this comparison is based on this first stage of our collaboration. It should be evaluated with more information will be available in upcoming months of the project. Additionally, different universities may have different organizational structures and cultural norms that influence their approach to research management.

The report identifies the factors that needed to improve in ACU TTO unit. The data show that **the employees have high trust in the team, the teams' competencies are seen higher than average level of the individual perception, and the employees are happy to work together.** However, **challenges** have also emerged, such as **the workload, the need for skilled workers, the ambiguity of job descriptions,** and areas of improvement in **project management skills.** In addition, since some of the employees are in administrative duties and others are in charge of research and development expertise, **their responsibilities need to be clearly defined.**

It has been stated that there are opportunities for **improvement in areas such as communication skills, level of the English language and project management skills.** Moreover, ACU TTO staff face challenges such as **lack of recognition by internal stakeholders, both the administrative staff and the researchers at ACU.**

Rather than the quantitative results, the focus group discussion gave us clear results that **the employees would like to develop project management skills in international level with good command of English.** On the other hand, they have emphasized that even if they have an opportunity to improve their skills, they

¹² *ibid.*

may face difficulties such as high workload, unclear job definitions and frameworks, and a scarcity of personnel.

One of the sub-themes that emerged in the focus group discussions was **the issue of not being recognized by internal stakeholders**, which directly affects the work of the office. However, with GEMSTONE project, they think that it can be an opportunity to reveal the activities and increase their visibility. In the answers given to the questions asked about LUND collaboration in the focus group, they emphasized that they were hopeful of this cooperation. “to monitor the processes in place (visiting ULUND)” and “to learn establish a collaboration” and “to have guidance” are their most important expectations.

It is observed that the common points in terms of features that are **open to improvement in their evaluations are areas such as lack of reporting, lack of staff, required continuous improvement**. When we look at these areas, we observe that office workers feel competent while defining their own competencies, however, these competencies are not reflected by the researchers working with them. Despite this, **it is emphasized by the researchers that the office workers work with devotion and are diligent in helping themselves, despite the small number of office workers**.

We have understood that an effective research management requires a multi-faceted approach that takes into account both institutional improvement and bottom-up demand mechanisms. Institutional improvement initiatives can be implemented to ensure that the necessary policies and resources are in place to support research activities. At the same time, bottom-up demand mechanisms can be utilized to ensure that research efforts are aligned with the needs and priorities of stakeholders. In order to ensure that these efforts are successful, it is important to address critical policy and staff improvement needs. **Policies must be developed that promote transparency (equal workload), accountability (clear and public work flows), and equitable distribution of resources (salary policy)**.

Staff must also be provided with the necessary training and support to effectively carry out their research-related duties. By addressing these areas of concern, organizations can create an environment that fosters innovation, collaboration, and high-quality research outcome.

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Documents available in English:

- Lund University Strategic Plan 2017-2026: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/strategic-plan-2017-2026.pdf>
- Lund University Research strategy 2017-2022: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2022-01/research-strategy-2017-2021.pdf> (this is currently being updated)
- Joint support for the University's participation in the EU framework programme: <https://www.staff.lu.se/sites/staff.lu.se/files/2021-07/Joint-support-for-the-Universitys-participation-in-Horizon%20Europe.pdf>
- General information on our support on research funding: <https://www.staff.lu.se/research-and-education/research-support/research-funding>

Useful documents only available in Swedish:

- Action plan for Lund University's collaboration with Europe 2021-2024: <https://www.medarbetarwebben.lu.se/sites/medarbetarwebben.lu.se/files/2021-02/handlingsplan-for-lu-samarbete-med-europa-2021-2024.pdf>
- Operational plan for the central university administration 2022 (see page 23, which describes the mandate for our division Research, Collaboration and innovation): <https://www.medarbetarwebben.lu.se/sites/medarbetarwebben.lu.se/files/2022-03/Gemensamma-forvaltningens-verksamhetsplan-2022.pdf>

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Annexes

Annex1: ACU Internal Fund

Directive for Scientific Research Projects Commission - (Internal Fund) evaluates the scientific research and infrastructure development project proposals that will be managed by Acıbadem University faculty members and researchers who have completed their doctorate or medical specialization training in accordance with the vision, mission and organizational values of the university, and approves the appropriateness of granting appropriations from the relevant academic year budget.

Acıbadem University offers a diverse range of scientific research and development projects to faculty members, researchers, and students alike. These projects encompass various scientific fields and are designed to promote collaborative efforts among faculty members from different disciplines and institutions.

These projects include initiatives that support graduate, doctoral, and medical specialization theses conducted in the Institutes and Faculty of Medicine, as well as those proposed by department heads in faculties or by heads of departments in colleges, institutes, and central directorates. These projects aim to improve the scientific research and development infrastructure of the relevant units.

Furthermore, Acıbadem University encourages research and development projects initiated by faculty members with partial or complete support from industrial organizations, as well as those that are supported by national institutions such as DPT, TUBITAK, and other relevant organizations.

International collaborations are also highly valued, and the university welcomes projects partially or fully supported by international organizations or those that fall within the scope of the European Union framework program. Additionally, projects aimed at enhancing the quality of education and training provided by Acıbadem University and implementing modern technologies are highly encouraged.

The university also supports patent-related projects and endeavours to increase the potential, number, and quality of Acıbadem University patents. Finally, projects initiated and carried out by students under the supervision of a faculty member are evaluated and supported within this context.

This fund is followed by a software programme called [BAPSİS](#). All the procedures are followed via the system. Different from LUND University, ACU TTO is responsible for following all steps of internal research fund shortly called as ABAPKO. Above mentioned Directive is followed for these kind of internal fund supporting for research projects between the budget of 5.000 TL and 200.000 TL.

All the external funded projects is followed [DAPSİS](#) software programme by the ACU TTO. [AVESİS](#) software programme is used by all academic staff and ACU TTO utilize this area to know about the researchers in details including research areas, publications, project experiences, IPs, etc.

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Research Services – External Funding

More than just a traditional grants office – a ‘hub for strategic considerations in research funding’

Support to management

- Help and information, strategic considerations, administration of processes

Monitor the funding landscape

- Keep the university up to date on developments in the national and international funding landscape

Helping researchers to apply

- Focus on high-impact grants (of strategic importance to Lund University)

Support throughout the project process

I am curious about EU financing

- Information seminars and individual meetings at any stage of interest

I am going to write an application

- Individual meetings to give initial facilitating info, tips and templates for the application
- Start-up and writing packages
- Additional information about announcements
- Tips and feedback on call match, consortium and draft applications
- Help with budget and co-financing calculation
- Answer administrative questions and portal issues

My project has been approved

- Contract preparations and contract issues
- Initial meeting with researcher and administrator/economist
- Support in reporting and preparation for audit
- Planning and coordination grants

My application has been rejected

- Review of the EU evaluation protocol
- Get support with a new application

Our support across pillars

Wider research funding support

Networks of research administrators and of financial administrators with EU-projects at department level		
<p>Legal support The legal counsel provide support and advice on legal issues, e.g. IP, consortium agreements</p>	<p>Innovation LU innovation provides advice and guidance on issues related to innovation & commercialisation</p>	<p>Ethics An ethics advisor gives research ethics support, available for applications and on-going projects</p>
<p>Open access and data management The libraries provide support on open access, data management plans</p>	<p>Security issues A security coordinator offers advice on, e.g. export control and dual use</p>	<p>Collaborations The Cooperation Office may provide project management and advise on consortium building with industry and public sector</p>
<p>Layout and graphic design Media-Tryck offers additional support with layout and graphic design of an application</p>	<p>Other programmes at other central units ERASMUS+ EIT-KIC</p>	<p>Gender issues One researcher and the HR section can provide some input on gender issues</p>

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Annex3: Competencies and Skills of ULUND Research Services Support Staff

Competencies

EU framework programme

Staff 1 (Research Funding Advisor)

- MSc in Chemical Engineering, Lund University; Postgraduate education in Medical sciences, worked both within the university world and in the private sector
- Broad knowledge of applications to many different financiers, national and international
- Competence in utilizing research and facilitating impact analysis
- Competence in communication and marketing
- Good LU knowledge
- Knowledge of the EU's research policy and funding
- Analytical ability and administrative experience
- Pedagogical and communicative skills
- Collaborative skills and knowledge in project management
- Creative and driven, ability to network
- Ability to present information in Swedish and English
- Is service-oriented, committed, flexible and problem-solving,
- Has initiative, drive, efficiency and is responsible
- Experience of collaboration and business development

Staff 2 (Research Funding Advisor)

- Broad education: master's degree in molecular biology, sociology degree, and B courses in English and literary studies
- Extensive experience in research funding and support activities.
- Good general education
- Good knowledge of LU
- Good administrative skills
- Good analytical skills
- Good communication and collaboration skills
- Initiative, drive, responsibility

Staff 3 (Research Funding Advisor)

- PhD in Chemistry from Imperial College London; Master of Research from Imperial College London; Master of Physics (with Photonics) from the University of St Andrews.
- Research training and participation in research applications and projects
- Lots of experience from EU funding
- Good knowledge of how research applications are evaluated
- English – very good knowledge, written and spoken
- Analytical ability
- Ability to work together
- Creative
- Ability to present information in English

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- Administrative experience

Staff 4 (Research Funding Advisor)

- PhD in Cognitive Science from Lund University, Master in Cognitive Science from Umeå University
- Driving and participating in research applications and projects
- Good LU knowledge
- Good analytical skills
- Good communication and collaboration skills
- Initiative, drive, responsibility and efficiency

Staff 5 (Research Funding Advisor – Financial)

- Background: Master's degree in economics with a focus on organization, management and financial control. Good accounting skills and several courses in leadership, employment law and contract law.
- Previous employer: Overall institutional finance, budget, forecast and follow-up as well as solid experience of working with external financing. Together with the head of department, I worked out a lean and high-performing administration and contributed to the successful development of the department with higher research output and higher employee satisfaction as a result.

Swedish funders

Staff 1 (Research Funding Advisor)

- PhD natural science
- English – very good knowledge, editorial experience
- Swedish language – very good knowledge, editorial experience
- Stylistic ability
- Analytical ability
- Organizational ability
- Ability to present information orally in Swedish and English
- Project management
- External/market communication, web/communication strategy
- Image/Graphics/Layout/Design (print/digital)

Staff 2 (Research Funding Advisor)

- PhD evolution/genetics
- Project manager training
- Teaching: in Sweden and internationally - from school grades up to doctoral students
- Project management: Managed large-scale field projects internationally - financing, leadership responsibilities. Responsibility for security, as well as for coordination between stakeholders.
- Author/writer/editor – many years of experience in writing in all its forms
- Reporting: reported to stakeholders and financiers in many contexts – in writing, statistics, through lectures.

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- Communication about research towards the wider public - as a writer, field biologist, scientific guide
- Application writing, extensive experience in reading and commenting on applications in all scientific fields
- Language: Swedish and English fluent since childhood, in writing from fiction to science (both as author and editor). German and French good understanding.
- Statistics and data analysis on a large scale

Staff 6 Research Funding Advisor – budget, accounting and auditing

Research service functional description	
Name	
Position	Research Funding Advisor – budget, accounting and auditing
Job duties	<p>Ongoing advice with an emphasis on financial issues primarily within the EU framework programme but also other funders, in the application phase and throughout the projects to final reporting; for example, when drawing up budgets, assisting with financial reporting, distribution of funds to partners in coordinated projects, etc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Go through projects before the commission's "audit visits" * Develop/draw up administrative procedures * financial matters of principle that affect external financing * Overall economic issues (which primarily relate to the EU framework programme) * LU's support money * Hold seminars, trainings, inform at kick-off meetings at the start of the project * Project certificate * More and more questions about rules that do not only apply to financial matters, e.g. amendments regarding change of partner, extension, etc * Support for applications and reporting in F & T Portal * Procure and be contact regarding Horizon projects for procured audit firm; until 2023-06-30 * Administration and participation in information meetings with external presenters. * Assist in filling out American forms * Maintains newsletters for economists who manage EU projects * The content of the Project Management H2020 and HEU websites * Start-up meetings
Responsibility	<p>Update/develop support for budgeting and reporting within the EU framework programme</p> <p>Review projects before audit visits from the Commission or European court of of auditors</p> <p>Update and hold the "Project management HEU for administrators" course</p> <p>Manage support money, planning grants and coordination grants, according to the rector's decision</p>

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	Content on the web pages about project management H2020 and HEU Template for start-up meetings
Powers	Request material according to the processing order Retrieve project-related informatio
Reports to	Head of Department
Internal contacts	Entire LU; Researchers and administrators with external funding, RÄ, Other sections within the administration, especially departments for law, finance, personnel, innovation, as well as faculty offices, heads of departments
External contacts	National SWARMA network, LERU, Swedish network for American financing, EARMA, NCPs at Vinnova / VR, Project coordinators from other organizations, EU Commission project / financial officers and auditors, the reference group for Legal and financial issues led by NCP at Vinnova for these questions.
Competence	Degree of Bachelor in public management 10 years as a department secretary at LU has given me an understanding of project management and the university's structure, the administrative line at LU, many years of practical work within FS with many different experiences from projects, courses and network meetings.
Date	2021-08-25

Staff 7: Research Funding Advisor, with an emphasis on the EU and impact

Research services functional description	
Name	Rickard Eksten
Position	Research Funding Advisor, with an emphasis on the EU and impact
Job duties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist researchers who want to participate in or coordinate projects within the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation; provide support in the application phase, during contract negotiation and during the course of the projects • Produce decision documents for head of department, project certificates for signature on applications, contract documents and contracts signed by head of office • Inform researchers, administrators and other stakeholders at LU about the EU framework programme and other possible research funding at personal meetings and through seminars, courses, presentations, blogs and mailings • Be involved in strategic initiatives aimed at special research areas, research groups and funding programs (e.g. impact) • Special responsibility for sub-areas within the framework program according to specific distribution (cluster 4 and associated partnerships, widening /ERA, mission on climate neutral cities) and primary HEU contact person for the faculty of social sciences and the school of economics and management

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible (together with colleague) for developing the support program for Pillar II (clusters and missions) as well as the EIC • List applications and projects at LU, as well as their status, forward reporting internally and externally, and archive relevant material • Support and provide information to the university management in strategic EU issues and questions about research funding • Contribute to the analysis and development of the support organization for research funding at LU and the management of these funds • Participate in relevant internal and external meetings and networks, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coordinate division's internal 'impact group' ○ LU annual horizon scanning: writing the EU chapter ○ Represent the SWARMA (Swedish Research Administrators and Managers Association) network in the Widening/ERA reference group ○ Member of SUHF (Swedish Association of HEIs) EU working group (current mandate until spring 2023) to monitor and analyze EU policy with bearing on Swedish higher education institutions, as well as highlight consequences and proposals for measures to SUHF's expert group for internationalization ○ Member in CESAER Task Force Sustainable Funding ○ Member of LERU's European research programme group
Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To summarize and convey the project conditions to the head of department and researchers before decisions on participation • To treat each application/project with discretion • To deal with every matter that comes in as soon as possible • To document the work so that colleagues can easily take over cases • To be continuously updated concerning above all the EU's framework programme • Diary keeping
Powers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To request material from researchers/administrators in order to prepare contract documents • To contact the head of office directly if necessary
Reports to	Head of Research Services
Internal contacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers and administrators who intend to participate/participate in EU projects • Prefects, heads of offices and equivalents • The university management and their secretaries • Other departments in the FSI division • Legal Department, Personnel Section, Finance Section • Ethics support and security officer • Librarians and research support at UB • Communicators

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The research administrator network at LU• Lärosäten Syd's Brussels office
External contacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• NCPs and Program Committee Members of the Framework Programme• Manager at Vinnova, VR and other research financiers• Administrative officers at the EU Commission in Brussels• Colleagues at other Swedish and foreign universities• Coordinators of EU projects where LU participates as a partner• Networks: national (SWARMA, SUHF) and international (LERU , CESAER , ERRIN)• Region Skåne's Brussels office• Consultants for educational efforts related to research funding
Competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Academic degree (Master of Arts in European Union Studies and French, from the University of Edinburgh; postgraduate Master in European Political and Administrative studies, from College of Europe)• Swedish and English in speech and writing• Experience in research funding and support activities• Good knowledge of EU research policy and programmes• Competence in utilization of research (impact)• Good general education• Good administrative skills• Good analytical skills• Good communication and collaboration skills• Initiative, drive, responsibility, service-oriented• Good LU knowledge
Date	

Annexe 4: Technology Transfer Office (TTO) Staff and Job Definitions

<p>Technology Transfer Office Manager</p>	<p>Business and Transactions of Commissions-AFDK Commission -ABAPKO Commission -Innovation Coord. Commission - Internationalization Commission -R&D and Intellectual Property Evaluation Commission - Strategic Planning Commission (data provision) - TEKMER Incubation Prog. Commissions</p>	<p>Transactions Regarding Internal Funds -Monitoring AFDK Works -Monitoring ABAPKO works -Reporting and presenting internal funds Following the BAPSYS system</p>	<p>Transactions Regarding External Funds -Monitoring the project application, execution and closing works - Introducing, announcing and monitoring the dissemination of the funds -Creating teams for the funds -Reporting and presenting the external funds- Monitoring of DAPSYS system-TUBITAK TTS system follow-up -TÜSEB TYBS system follow-up - EU ECAS system follow-up - Other fund institution project systems follow-up - UIL funds follow-up</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs - Monitoring the social media accounts of TTO -Monitoring the website -Following the organization and management of events -Participating in activities for the representation of the office, participating in class invitations -Negotiating with partnerships that will enable the university to take part in projects -Providing cooperation development and networking management - Information for visibility and data provision</p>	<p>Other Cross-cutting WorksIn-house - HR UnitMonitoring the processes of scholars and other employees working on projects withPurchasing Unit Monitoring project-based purchases with - Financial Affairs UnitMonitoring project-based budget expenditure reports with -Quality Unit provision of data on research data withCorporate communications monitoring visibility activities with - Research Centers and Laboratories Establishing infrastructure-based collaborations with With Academic UnitsMonitoring of UIL consultations -to the General Secretariat adding the obligations arising from the legislation to the operationExternal - Conducting possible</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting -Compilation of research data requested by index-ranking-classification systems (Strategic Plan, KİDR, YÖK, TÜİK, GYÜE, THE, QS, etc.) -Following personnel performance indicators -Following and updating administrative workflows -Organizing all research-related reports and follow-up -Filing the relevant outputs, creating and updating the electronic archive in the common area.</p>
<p>Business Development and Patent Specialist</p>	<p>IP Administrative Affairs and Transactions-Creation of Intellectual and Industrial Property portfolio -Creation and implementation of commercialization models for the portfolio -Patent/Utility Model/Design applications and follow-up through a proxy company -Patent innovation preliminary research -Management of IP contract processes -Following legal regulations UIL Administrative Affairs and Transactions -Business development for UIL consultancy -Management and negotiation of UIL contract processes -Following legal regulations -Other consultancy, training, program development, etc. research oriented business development</p>	<p>Commission Business and Transactions R&D and Intellectual Property Values *Making the secretariat of the commission (agenda, decision, IPC, decision notifications) -Receiving and evaluating UIL consultancy requests - Receiving and evaluating other consultancy requests -Receiving and evaluating the IP requests -Reporting up-to-date data to the commission about the UIL and IP</p>	<p>IP Content and Consulting Works- - Making one-to-one meetings with academicians and students about inventions - Organizing consultancy, training and informing - Following up and announcing patent-based project calls and conducting commercialization negotiations -One-on-one meetings with academics about academic consultancy - Conducting meetings with companies for UIL - Following up, announcing and writing projects based on UILs</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs -Patent portfolio data tracking and announcement -UIL consultancy data tracking and announcement-Following and announcing commercialization activities -Negotiating with partnerships that will enable the university to take part in projects</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts -Incubation ProgramsProviding information on IP and UIL issues, ensuring cooperation development - FMH and UIL consultancyRecognition and promotion of academic staff for - Evaluation of outputs from research projects within the scope of IP</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting - Keeping and tracking patent utility model and design data related to IP - Keeping and tracking data for UIL consultancy -Filing related outputs, creating and updating electronic archives in the common area</p>

<p>Business Development and Support Funds Specialist</p>	<p>Administrative Affairs and Transactions Regarding Projects -Following up research funds and creating project teams for the funds, providing technical support in project writing -Tracking the application, execution and closing of projects as documents and data - Following up DAPSIS data entry and reporting</p>	<p>Human Resources Infrastructure for Research Funds -Keeping and tracking researcher information as data -Making one-on-one interviews with researchers - Creating and following up research teams for funds - Following new funds, announcing and matching them with researchers - Organizing events for calls for funds -Recognizing and promoting academic staff for UIL advisory services Physical Resource Infrastructure for Research Funds Following up the existing research infrastructure (research centers and laboratories) - Following up the infrastructure opportunities for services for companies</p>	<p>Transactions Regarding External Funds -Following the works on project application, execution and closing -Introducing, announcing and disseminating the funds -Evaluation and monitoring of research outputs -Creating research teams regarding the funds - Making reports and presentations</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs - Management of social media accounts -Management of the website -Organization and management of events - Creation of fund promotion materials-Creating research-based promotional materials for academic staff - Establishing partnerships that will enable the university to take part in projects</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts-Reporting based on the data of all processes of the projects (application, acceptance, closing, etc.) -Controlling the filing of the project documents -Incubation programs Informing about the funding opportunities and developing cooperation - Evaluation of the project outputs with the relevant modules</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting -Compilation of all data requested by index-ranking systems related to research -Compilation of all data requested by index-ranking systems subject to research (strategic plan, KİDR, YÖK, TUIK, GYÜE, THE, QS, etc.) -Filing of relevant outputs , creation and updating of electronic archives in the common area</p>
<p>Research Support Funds Specialist</p>	<p>ABAPKO-Commission secretariat (Agenda, decision, evaluation, official letter) - Receipt and execution of applications (Application notification, acceptance notification, evaluation notification) - Execution of reporting procedures (interim report, final report, closing procedures) - Keeping ABAPKO Data - BAPSIS - Ensuring the control of bursary transactions Administrative Affairs and Transactions Regarding Projects - Following up the application, execution and closing of the projects - Using DAPSIS</p>	<p>AFDK -Monitoring of the Commission secretariat (Agenda, decision, evaluation, official letter) - Receiving and Execution of Applications (application notification, acceptance notification, evaluation notification)</p>	<p>Transactions Regarding External Funds -Following up the works on project application, execution and closing -Introducing, announcing and disseminating the funds - Creating teams for the funds -Reporting and presenting external funds</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs - Management of the website - Creation of internal and external fund promotion materials</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts-Reporting based on the data of all processes of the projects (application, acceptance, closing, etc.) - Controlling the filing of the project documents - Incubation programs Informing about the funding opportunities and developing cooperation - Evaluating the project outputs with the relevant modules - Following up the ABAPKO scholarship payments with the HR Unit</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting - Compilation of all data requested by the index-ranking systems of the research -Preparation of internal and external data presentations -Filing of relevant outputs, creation and updating of electronic archives in the common area</p>

TEKMER Manager	<p>TEKMER Administrative Affairs and Transactions - Following up the funds that TEKMER can apply for - Performing cooperation studies for joint incubation programs -Following up the processes with the institutions and organizations that cooperated during the program process -Preparing data presentations-Executing the TEKMER project (purchasing, reporting, etc.)</p>	<p>Administrative Affairs and Transactions of TEKMER Companies -Following up the rent payment and land use of companies -Following and meeting the administrative needs of the companies -Ensuring the companies to meet with the investors -Organization, monitoring and finalizing the evaluation processes of the entrepreneurs-Preparation and submission of Institution Incentive documents for approval -Follow-up of incubation graduates - Following up the data of the incubator - -Managing the promotion and business development processes of entrepreneurs</p>	<p>Business and Transactions of Incubation Programs-Creating and announcing the program call - Making service purchases - Evaluation of applications - Executing TEKMER Incubation Program activities - Executing TÜBİTAK BIGGHEALTH Implementing Organization activities</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs -Following the management of social media accounts -Following the management of the website -Organization and management of events - Visual designspreparation</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts - Organization of entrepreneurship trainings -Direction of academic consultancy services and IP needs within the incubation program - Direction of prototyping services -Directing entrepreneurs to appropriate funds</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting - Archiving applications and information of entrepreneurs - Preparing internal and external data presentations - Following the progress reports of entrepreneurs - Preparing and following up one pagers -Reporting the project to KOSGEB - Reporting to TEKMER Executive Committee</p>
TEKMER Entrepreneurship Assistant Specialist	<p>TEKMER Administrative Affairs and Transactions - TEKMER document and archive follow-up -Program processes follow-up - Commission/Board secretariat -Operational works</p>	<p>Administrative Affairs and Transactions of TEKMER Companies -Organization of entrepreneurs' evaluation processes Keeping incubation data - Carrying out the business and operations of the promotion processes of entrepreneurs</p>	<p>Business and Transactions of Incubation Programs-Executing the work and operations of the BIGGHEALTH Program call -Executing the works and operations of the TEKMER Incubation Program call</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs - Monitoring social media accounts-Organization and follow-up of events - Execution of visibility of incubation programs</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts -Following the entrepreneurship trainings -Executing the operational works of the events</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting - Archiving applications and information of entrepreneurs - Providing data for internal and external presentations - Following the progress reports of entrepreneurs - Preparing and monitoring one pagers *Filing related outputs, creating and updating electronic archives in the common area</p>
Biodesign and Business Development Officer (Biodesign Center)	<p>Biodesign Center Administrative Affairs and Operations Execution of the project request processes coming to the center - Projecting the requests by submitting them to the Intellectual Property Rights and R&D Commission - Execution of the work and transactions of the approved projects -Business development and negotiation for IP Commercialization - Business development and negotiation for design-based UIL consultancy</p>	<p>Business and Transactions of Biodesign Center Projects - Planning the project process (team, contract processes), realization of the project (prototyping) and finalization (reporting, presentation) - Conducting internal and external meetings for new collaborations</p>	<p>Biodesign Center UIL and Commercialization Transactions - Writing Intellectual and Industrial Rights claims - Following contracts in UIL and Commercialization processes Identifying stakeholders and companies specific to the project - Management of outputs such as academic publications, commercialization intellectual and property rights</p>	<p>Visibility Affairs - Management of Biodesign Center social media accounts - Management of Biodesign Center website - Organization and management of events</p>	<p>Intersecting Jobs with Other Experts -Providing training, mentoring and consultancy within the scope of incubation and ASEGEM programs - IP Process Management and organization of applications related to the center - Execution of commercialization processes related to the center - Contacting companies for UIL activities - Providing funding suggestions for projects</p>	<p>Data Tracking and Reporting -Reporting the project revenues of the biodesign center -Filing the relevant outputs, creating and updating the electronic archive in the common area</p>

ACU TTO Administrative Jobs	WORKS ON INTERNAL FUNDS			WORKS ON EXTERNAL FUNDS	
STAFF AND JOB DEFINITIONS	AFDK	ABAPKO	TUBITAK	TUSEB	EUROPEAN UNION
Projects Financial Affairs Specialist		<p>*Scholarship Procedures (Recruitment, payment transactions and referral to the HR Unit)</p> <p>*Filing the relevant outputs, creating and updating the electronic archive in the common area</p>	<p>*Scholarship Procedures (Recruitment, payment transactions and referral to the HR Unit)</p> <p>*TUBITAKData entry to the Transfer Tracking System (TTS) *Filing the relevant outputs, creating and updating the electronic archive in the common area</p>	<p>TUSEB Project Management System (TYBS) follow-up *Project Contract Transactions (Bank guarantee and account opening transactions) *Invoice Payment Transactions (Receiving invoice approvals, preparing instructions, performing payment transactions)</p> <p>*Scholarship Transactions (Recruitment, payment transactions and referral to the HR Unit) *Data entry to the TYBS system *Reporting Operations (supplying documents for YMM reports, closing procedures) *Keeping TUSEB Data</p>	
Projects Administrative Affairs Officer	<p>*Commission Secretariat (Agenda, decision, official letter, notice of the Executive Board) * Receiving and Execution of Applications(Application notification, acceptance notification, payment notification) * Payment of Acceptances(Payment transactions with proof documents) *Keeping AFDK Data *Filing the relevant outputs, creating and updating the electronic archive in the common area</p>				
Projects Financial Affairs Specialist			<p>* TÜBİTAK Project Management System (TTS) follow-up *Project Contract Transactions (Account opening transactions)</p> <p>*Invoice Payment Transactions(Receiving invoice approvals, preparing instructions, performing payment transactions) *Data entry to the Transfer Tracking System (TTS)</p> <p>*Reporting Operations (supplying documents to YMM reports, closing transactions) *Retention of TÜBİTAK Data</p>	<p>* TUSEB Project Management System (TYBS) follow-up *Project Contract Transactions (Bank guarantee, account opening transactions) *Invoice Payment Transactions (Receiving invoice approvals, preparation of orders, realization of payment transactions)</p> <p>*Scholarship Transactions (Recruitment, payment transactions and referral to HR Unit) -*Data entry to TYBS system</p> <p>*Reporting Operations (Providing documents for YMM reports, closing procedures) *Retention of TUSEB Data</p>	<p>*Buying processes (Invoicing of purchases from the Purchasing Unit) *Invoice Payment Transactions (Receiving invoice approvals, preparing instructions, performing payment transactions) * Scholarship Procedures (recruitment, payment transactions and referral to the HR Unit)</p> <p>*Follow-up of Budget Crimes *Support for Preparation of Financial Reports *Retention of Data *Filing of relevant outputs, creation and updating of electronic archives in the common area</p>

